

MICROORGANISMS FOUND IN THE SOIL

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the types of microorganisms in the soils, the development of microorganisms, their role in increasing soil fertility, symbiotic relationships, processes of ammonification and nitrification.*

Keywords: *microorganism, microflora, bacteria, microbes, the structure of the soil, aerobes, biological nitrogen, anaerobes, saprophytes, symbiosis, mycorrhiza, ammonification, nitrification.*

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that different districts on Earth lives and each of them has a unique character and has a place in biocenosis. The importance of microorganisms is unique. Their diversity is found to have a lot of features when studied and activity learned. In particular, there is an ability to provide the most important nitrogen or phosphorus for plants. In the roots of the plant live many bacteria that can convert molecular nitrogen in the air to biological nitrogen (bio nitrogen). They are called bacteria that absorb nitrogen with a general name. The more the bacteria in the soil are more fertile, the higher the yield.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Soil contains a large number of microorganisms, meaning that 1 g of soil contains millions or billions of microorganisms. It is much more than air and water. There are various types of bacteria, actinomycetes, yeasts, algae and simple animals in the soil, and scientists estimate that 3-5 tons of bacteria can be found in a layer of up to 25 cm deep in a plowed hectare of land. The distribution of bacteria in the soil depends on the nature of the soil. Microorganisms multiply greatly due to plant and animal remains that fall into the soil. The number of microorganisms in the soil varies depending on the type of soil, physical and chemical properties and climatic conditions. There is a large number of microorganisms on the surface of the soil, and their number decreases as it goes down. Microorganisms are abundant in the 10-15 cm layer, because there is no direct sunlight, and there is sufficient nutrition and moisture. And in the deep layers, they are less, because the soil acts as a natural filter and does not transfer bacteria to the groundwater. Plant and animal residues are decomposed with the participation of microorganisms capable of absorbing cellulose, pentoses, starch, pectin substances, etc., and ultimately turn into water with carbon dioxide. Microorganisms play a big role in the nitrogen cycle in nature. Animals make the nitrogenous compounds they need from plant proteins. Animal and vegetable proteins are mineralized under the influence of bacteria, first turning into ammonia, then nitrites and nitrates. Both ammonium salts and nitrates are nutrients for higher plants, which use these salts to make proteins in their bodies. Bacteria also mineralize other

biogenic elements. They decompose organic phosphorus compounds and increase mineral phosphorus compounds in water bodies and soil. Under the influence of bacteria, organic compounds of sulfur are also converted into minerals.

It is the result of the activity of aerobes, anaerobes, saprophytes, nitrifiers, nitrogen fixers, cellulose decomposers, sulfur bacteria, spore-forming and non-spore-forming representatives of different turbidity groups. The number of microorganisms also changes depending on the seasons. Bacteria are abundant around the root system of plants, most of which are aerobic, non-spore-forming, rod-shaped representatives. Bacteria belonging to this generation absorb carbohydrates, organic acids and synthesize a number of vitamins. Plants absorb these vitamins.

Biocenosis of bacteria changes when organic substances in the soil are decomposed. First of all, when there are fast and easily decomposing substances in the soil, mainly non-spore-forming rod-shaped bacteria are widespread, and later they are replaced by spore-forming aerobic bacteria. When the soil is well cultivated, there is an increase in the number of bacteria. Bacteria, fungi, infusoria, plant roots and a number of animals play an extremely important role in the process of soil formation.

Ammonification is a process in which ammonia is formed as a result of the decomposition of protein, ammonium acids and other nitrogen-containing substances. This process is also called nitrogen mineralization. Because the resulting ammonia is again converted into a mineral state with the help of nitrifying bacteria. Ammonification of proteins with the participation of aerobic, anaerobic bacteria and fungi has been established. Representatives of the *Pseudomonas* family and representatives of the *Bacillus* family belong to the microorganisms showing special activity in this process.

Nitrification is a process in which ammonia formed from the decomposition of organic matter in soil, manure, and water is oxidized to nitrite and then to nitrates. The first stage of nitrification is carried out by representatives of five genera: *Nitrosomonas*, *Nitrosococcus*, *Nitrosospira*, *Nitrosolobus* and *Nitrosovibrio*, while the second stage is carried out by representatives of the genera *Nitrobacter*, *Nitrospira*, *Nitrococcus*. All these processes serve to increase the fertility of the soil, improve its composition and increase the yield of plants.

Nitrogen is the main element that takes a higher place than elements such as phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, iron, and sulfur in increasing the productivity of agricultural plants. But the molecular state of nitrogen cannot be absorbed directly by plants. Basically, only its mineralized form is absorbed by plants. It is in the soil that there is a mineral form, and other forms fly into the air. Therefore, the transition of nitrogen in the soil from one state to another is important for plant nutrition. Nitrogen-fixing microorganisms are azotofixators - microorganisms that absorb molecular nitrogen from the atmosphere and convert it into organic compounds. They are bacteria belonging to the genus *Phisobium* that live symbiotically with leguminous plants. 100250 kg or more of nitrogen per year is accumulated in each hectare planted with leguminous plants. Biological nitrogen accumulated in alfalfa roots increases soil fertility, increases the amount of humus in the soil, and reduces the hydrolytic acidity of the soil. Actinomycetes, which form nodules on the roots of non-legume plants, are also nitrogen-fixing microorganisms. *Clostridium*, free-living spore anaerobic bacteria in soil and water bodies, aerobic microorganisms - *azotobacter*, and oligonitrophils are active nitrogen-accumulating microorganisms. Most species of blue-green algae (*Nostoc*, *Anabaena*, etc.), some orange-red sulfur bacteria and green bacteria are also active nitrogen-fixing microorganisms. 80 species of

nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae are known, 45 of which are distributed in the soils and water bodies of Central Asia. Some types of fungi, yeasts, spirochetes and others participate in the accumulation of atmospheric nitrogen. Nitrogen-fixing microorganisms are of great importance in the cycle of nitrogen in nature, in particular, in providing plants with available nitrogen, that is, in making atmospheric nitrogen usable by plants.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it should be said that microorganisms absorbing molecular nitrogen are extremely important. The nitrogen reserve in the atmosphere is inexhaustible, there are 8 million tons of nitrogen in the air at 1 km of the earth's surface. This nitrogen, which cannot be assimilated by plants, is assimilated by microorganisms and brought to an acceptable state for plants. Various types of nitrogen bacteria: sulfur bacteria, red (purple) bacteria, cyanobacteria, etc., are involved in this process. This process, which is the result of symbiosis of plants and microorganisms, is important. There are other nitrogen-fixing microorganisms capable of establishing symbiotic associations with plants, especially legumes and grasses, in the form of ectosymbiosis (where the microorganism is outside the plant) or endosymbiosis (where the microorganism is inside the plant). Most of the fixed nitrogen in dry ecosystems comes from symbiotic associations of progenitor bacteria.

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